

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MASAKWA****FIRST NAME: RINGO STAR****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What does the term research specifically mean?

- Strong beliefs, feelings and interests that inform solutions to a problem.
- A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher but also others want to solve.¹**
- Reporting and reasoning grounded on personal values and emotions.
- Restricted critical thinking about evidence and reasoning.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 18-20.

2. What is the correct sequence in defining project research?

- Question, Topic, Problem, Working Hypothesis.
- Problem, Topic, Question, Working Hypothesis.
- Question, Problem, Working Hypothesis, Topic.
- Topic, Question, Problem, Working Hypothesis.²**

3. What is the main purpose of data analysis validity?

- Formulate hypotheses and research questions.
- Send aggregate summaries of the findings to participants who requested this information.
- Describe the data analysis techniques that are used to test similar hypotheses.
- Provide evidence of congruence by showing how data analysis methods fit the questions being asked or the hypotheses being examined in the dissertation.³**

² Kate L. Turabian, 23-33.

³ Sampson, James P. 2017. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University), 48-53.

4. When does the researcher bias most likely not occur?

- Believes in the inherent relationship among variables or the efficacy of a theory or intervention, irrespective of the findings obtained in the dissertation.
- Selecting a research question that does not satisfy an ulterior motive.⁴**
- Selecting specific variables, measures, treatments, participants, and data analyses that increases the chances of obtaining specific predetermined findings.
- Selectively emphasizing specific sources from the professional literature review in the discussion of the findings.

5. Which of the following concepts is optional in a dissertation?

- Dedication.⁵**
- Acknowledgments.
- Review of Literature.
- Biography.

⁴ Ibid., 15-18.

⁵ Ibid., 28.

6. What types of measures are typically used in quantitative research?

- Questionnaires using predominately open-ended items.
- Interviews using structured, partially structured, or unstructured questions.
- Unobtrusive observations, instruments, and questionnaires using predominantly fixed response items.⁶**
- Focus groups.

7. Delimitations are anticipated constraints in the interpretation of the findings of the dissertation research whereas limitations are unanticipated constraints in data interpretation. Which of the following is not true of a delimitation?

- Delimitations indicate boundaries associated with the methods of the dissertation including quasi-experimental research designs restrictions.
- The delimitations help to shape the readers' expectations for the dissertation research and not judge whether or not the discussion of the findings is limited to the actual scope of the dissertation research.⁷**
- The delimitation constrains the generalizability of the findings.

⁶ Ibid., 44.

⁷ Ibid., 56-58.

- The delimitation constrains the plausibility of the findings.

8. What is the appropriate referencing for a journal article from the list below?

- 9. Ben Mercer, “Specters of Fascism: The Rhetoric of Historical Analogy in 1968,” *Journal of Modern History* 88, no. 1 (March 2016): 98.⁸**
9. Ben Mercer, The Rhetoric of Historical Analogy in 1968 “Specters of Fascism:,” *Journal of Modern History* 88, no. 1 (March 2016): 98
- . Ben Mercer, “Specters of Fascism: no. 1 (March 2016): 98 The Rhetoric of Historical Analogy in 1968,” *Journal of Modern History* 88.
- . Ben Mercer, “Specters of Fascism:,” *Journal of Modern History* 88, no. 1 (March 2016): 98; The Rhetoric of Historical Analogy in 1968.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 156.

9. The main features of good essay, report or article are:

- Original word and engaging voice.
- Stimulating ideas.
- Logical organization.
- All of the above.**⁹

10. The key aspects of giving a successful speech focus on;

- Stand curved and bold.
- Speak loudly and clearly.**¹⁰
- Look up as infrequently as you can.
- Fold your hands and avoid the audience.

⁹ Laurent, Cleenewerck, and Gulma Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021,30.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 368.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Laurent, Cleenewerck, and Gulma Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.
- Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.